

QUASI STATIC COMPRESSIVE RESPONSE OF CFRP HONEYCOMB WITH PMI FOAM FILLERS

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Abstract

A hybrid core made from square carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) honeycomb filled with polymethacrylimide (PMI) foams was proposed and prepared. Quasi static compression tests and numerical simulations were conducted and effects of the geometric parameters and foam fillers on the compressive response and energy absorption of the core were discussed. The results show that the foam fillers significantly improved the compressive properties of the honeycomb and the geometrical parameters affect the compressive response of the core. The research can guide the design and optimization of lightweight and energy efficient core structures.

Structure preparation

- The CFRP sheets with the thickness of $t_w=0.4$ mm was prepared via resin transfer molding method and the sheets were cut into rectangular pieces as sketched in Fig. 1(a).
- The slotted rectangular pieces were joined together as shown in Fig. 1(b) to assemble the square honeycomb. The joints between pieces were bounded using a low viscosity epoxy adhesive.
- The PMI foams were cut into blocks with the dimension of length and width equal to l_w and height equals to h_c . Then the foam blocks with epoxy resin on the surfaces were inserted into the honeycomb and lastly the assembled core was cured at 60 °C for 2 hours. The prepared core structure with $l_w=10$ mm and $h_c=20$ mm is shown in Fig. 1(d).

Fig. 1 Preparation process of CFRP honeycomb with foam fillers

Numerical model

Fig. 2 Numerical model of CFRP honeycomb with foam fillers under compression

Property	Value
0/90° elastic modulus	$E_0=4.8$ GPa
45° elastic modulus	$E_{45}=6.0$ GPa
0° tensile strength	$\sigma_0^t=195$ MPa
0° compressive strength	$\sigma_0^c=191$ MPa
45° tensile strength	$\sigma_{45}^t=103$ MPa
45° compressive strength	$\sigma_{45}^c=153$ MPa
Poisson's ratio	$\nu_h=0.16$
Density	$\rho_h=1450$ kg/m ³

Table 1 Material properties of CFRP

Fig. 3 Comparison between numerical and experimental results

Properties	Foam A	Foam B	Foam C
Density(kg/m ³)	52	75	110
Compressive modulus(MPa)	47	71	119
Compressive strength(MPa)	0.99	2.0	3.0
Tensile modulus(MPa)	74	120	200
Tensile strength(MPa)	1.7	2.6	4.1
Shear modulus(MPa)	23	30	70
Shear strength(MPa)	0.92	1.6	2.7

Table 2 Material properties of PMI foams

Results and discussions

Compressive deformation process

Energy absorbing process

- Before the honeycomb failed, the energy absorption of the core is dominated by the honeycomb.
- After the honeycomb failed, the plastic deformation of the foam fillers showed up gradually under the effects of the compressive loading and honeycomb deformation.
- Energy absorbed by the foam fillers is much fewer than that by the honeycomb

Effects of h_c

- The core height has no effect on the linear elastic response and buckling initiation of the hybrid core.
- with the increase of the core height, the peak stress decreased while the plateau stress increased.
- With the increase of the core height, the specific energy absorption also increased.

Effects of l_w

- with the increase of l_w , the elastic modulus, the peak stress as well as the plateau stress of the core decreased.
- the specific energy absorption of the core increased with the decrease of l_w .

Effects of foam fillers

- the foam fillers have a significant effect on the peak stress and plateau stress of the core.
- with the increase of the foam density, the peak stress and the plateau stress were also increased.
- the foam fillers dramatically improved the energy efficiency of the honeycomb core.

Conclusions

Square CFRP honeycomb cores with PMI foam fillers were proposed and prepared. The quasi static compressive properties of the core were analyzed by compressive tests and numerical simulations. The PMI foam fillers significantly improved the compressive properties of the CFRP honeycomb by increasing the compressive strength and specific energy absorption efficiency.